

***N,N*-Dimethyl-4-amino pyridine (DMAP) as a novel and sensitive reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of copper(II)**

G. V. S. R. Pavan Kumar^{*a}, T. Chandra Sekhar^b, V. Luke Paul^b and B. Sreerama Murty^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, M. V. G. R. College of Engineering, Chintalavalasa, Vizianagaram-535 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : prs_ganti@yahoo.co.in, sreeram6000@gmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Govt. Degree College, Tekkali-530 046, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Abstract : The present work deals with the spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) with *N,N*-dimethyl-4-amino pyridine (DMAP) as a chromogen. This method developed by the authors is found to be simple, accurate and precise for the determination of copper(II) by spectrophotometry. It was noticed that, during the reaction in aqueous media, between copper(II) and DMAP, an instantaneous, stable, clear ink blue colored product was formed without any precipitate or turbidity. The resultant ink blue colored product showed a maximum absorbance at 670 nm. Beer's law was found to be obeyed up to 30 mg of copper(II). Correlation factor was found to be 0.9862; SD and RSD were found to be well within the prescribed limits. Copper in other oxidation states other than +2, did not show such reaction with the chromogen DMAP. Hence it is concluded that the method developed by the authors is sensitive, advantageous and useful for the determination of copper(II) by spectrophotometry using DMAP as a reagent. The other foreign metal ions such as Fe^{II}, Ni^{II}, Sn^{II}, Sn^{IV}, Co^{II}, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ag^I did not interfere in the determination.

Keywords : Copper(II), DMAP, spectrophotometry.

Introduction

Copper exists as copper(I), copper(II) and copper(III). It was also reported in literature that copper also exhibits IV and V oxidation states. Out of all the reported oxidation states, copper(II) is found to be the most stable state and the literature survey indicates many methods and reagents for the determination copper(II) by volumetric, spectrophotometric, electro analytical and atomic absorption spectrophotometric methods.

Neocuproine, chloro phenyl glyoxime, 2-acetylpyridine-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone, 4-(2'-benzothiazolylazo)-salicylic acid, 5,8-dihydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone, dithizaone, ferrozine etc., were cited in literature to be some reagents used as chromogens for the determination of copper(II) by earlier workers¹. These processes are found to involve tedious procedures and costly reagents for the determination of copper(II). A survey of literature indicated that copper(II) exhibited an instantaneous stable

and clear intense ink blue color with 10% aqueous pyridine². The resulting blue colored solution by the reaction between copper(II) solution and 10% pyridine solution showed a maximum absorbance at 650.2 nm². In the light of the above reported work, the authors conducted experiments for the determination of copper(II) with derivatives of pyridine. During the course of such experiments, it was found that copper(II) exhibited an instantaneous clear and stable ink blue color with DMAP. Copper in other oxidation states other than +2, did not show such a colour reaction with the chromogen, DMAP. The absorption studies were performed in detail. The intense ink blue colored product formed between copper(II) and DMAP has shown an absorption maximum (λ_{\max}) at 670 nm and since the chromogen DMAP is colourless, there are no spectral interferences of chromogen DMAP.

4-Dimethyl amino pyridine³⁻⁶ (DMAP) is a derivative of pyridine with the established chemical structure as

shown below :

$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{NC}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$ *N,N*-Dimethyl-4-aminopyridine

The resultant shift in wavelength of maximum absorbance from pyridine as reported by earlier workers (650.2 nm)² to present 670 nm with DMAP can be attributed to the fact that the two methyl groups are of electron releasing nature causing a bathochromic shift (red shift). DMAP has a molecular mass of 122.17 g mole and a melting point range of $110\text{--}113 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. DMAP can be prepared in a two-step process from pyridine. In the first step, pyridine is oxidized to 4-pyridyl pyridinium cation. This cation then reacts with dimethyl amine⁵. However, the reagent DMAP is also commercially available in a pure state.

Experimental

Absorbance measurements :

Materials :

Preparation of 0.01 M copper(II) sulphate solution :

An adequate amount, 0.2496 g of copper(II) sulphate penta hydrate (mol. wt. = 249.68) was weighed and dissolved by the addition of a minimum quantity of double distilled water and 1 ml of glacial acetic acid. The solution was made up to the mark in a 100 ml volumetric flask and standardized¹.

Preparation of 5% DMAP solution : An adequate amount, 5 g of DMAP, is dissolved in double distilled water and the resulting solution is made up to the mark in a 100 ml volumetric flask³⁻⁶.

All the chemicals used were of AR grade only. For the preparation of all the solutions, double distilled water was used.

An Elico SL 150 UV Vis double beam spectrophotometer with matched set of glass cuvette was used for experimentation.

Recommended procedure for the determination of

copper(II) with the reagent DMAP :

An aliquot of copper(II) solution was mixed with 1 ml of 5% DMAP solution, to obtain an instantaneous, stable and clear ink blue colored product. The mixture is made up to the mark in a 100 ml volumetric flask and the spectra were taken for an aliquot of the solution with a matched set of cuvettes, which showed a maximum absorbance at 670 nm (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of the ink blue colored product obtained by the reaction between copper(II) and DMAP.

Results and discussion

The optical characteristics and validation data reports are presented in Table 1. The reaction between copper(II) solution and 5% DMAP solution produced an instantaneous, stable and clear ink blue color. There was no turbidity or precipitate. The ink blue colour solution

Table 1. Optical characteristics and validation data

Parameter	Reported value
Time of reaction	Instantaneous
Product	Clear, no turbidity or precipitate
λ_{max} (nm)	670
Beer's law limit (mg/L)	Up to 30
Molar absorptivity ($\text{cm}^{-1} \text{ L M}^{-1}$)	100
Correlation coefficient	0.9862
Relative standard deviation (%)	0.8
Limit of detection (mg/L)	0.0026
Limit of quantification (mg/L)	0.008

showed a maximum absorbance at 670 nm. Since DMAP is colorless, no spectral interference was found. There is no overlap of spectra of other components used such as reagent *etc.* Copper in other oxidation states other than +2, did not show such reaction with the chromogen DMAP. The ink blue colour developed was found to be stable for more than 24 h. The earlier workers² used 10% pyridine with λ_{max} of 650.2 nm to a limit of detection up to 22.4721 mg level². However with the derivative of pyridine (DMAP), the intensity of the instantaneous ink blue colour formed was found to be increased as observed by λ_{max} (670 nm) and the limit of detection up to 30 mg as seen in the calibration curve. Hence the proposed method is more sensitive for detection of copper(II) and the quantity of chromogen used was also found to be less with the derivative chromogen (DMAP) when compared to pyridine used by earlier workers². The interferences of foreign metal ions such as Fe^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Sn^{II}, Sn^{IV}, Ag^I was not found, as such this method can safely be employed for determination of copper(II) in specific alloys. As a test case, analysis of brass was done and accurate results were obtained.

Effect of temperature :

The color reaction between copper(II) solution and DMAP was studied at different temperatures and it was found that over the range of temperatures under investigation, the absorbance measurements were constant. It indicates that the reaction is independent on variation in temperature range up to 60 °C.

Effect of time :

In aqueous medium stable intense ink blue color was obtained immediately. In hydrochloric acid, sulphuric acid and phosphoric acid media below 2 *N* overall strength, pale ink blue color was observed and above 2 *N* no color was observed. In alkaline medium formation of precipitate was noticed. Hence the authors recommend aqueous medium for the detection of copper(II).

Beer's law was found to obeyed up to 30 mg/L of copper(II) sulphate (Fig. 2). The molar extinction coefficient was calculated to be 100 cm⁻¹ L M⁻¹. Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were found to be 0.0026 mg/L and 0.008 mg/L respectively. Correlation factor was calculated as 0.9686. Relative stan-

Fig. 2. Calibration curve for the determination of copper(II).

Fig. 3. Variation in the absorbance measurements with time.

ard deviation (RSD) calculated for ten measurements for the sample of copper(II) was found to be 0.8%. The lower values of RSD indicate the precision and reproducibility of the method developed by the authors. It was found from the data that the LOQ values calculated were three times greater than that of LOD. All these analytical method validation procedures indicate that the method developed by the authors is quite suitable for the determination of copper(II) in aqueous solutions using DMAP as a chromogen by spectrophotometry. The chromogen is also available in the market, hence its synthesis can be avoided.

Conclusions

An instantaneous, stable and clear ink blue color is produced by the reaction between copper(II) solution and 5% DMAP solution. The resulting ink blue colored produce showed λ_{max} at 670 nm. Copper in other oxidation states than +2, did not show such reaction with the chromogen DMAP. Beer's law was found to valid up to 30 mg/L. The molar extinction coefficient was found to be $100 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ L M}^{-1}$. Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were found to be 0.0026 mg/L and 0.008 mg/L respectively. Correlation factor was calculated and reported as 0.9686. Relative standard deviation calculated for ten measurements for the sample of copper(II) was found to be 0.8%. The optical characteristics and validation data are presented in Table 1.

From all the data, it is concluded by the authors, that the method developed is suitable, novel, sensitive and advantageous over the earlier reported methods for the determination of copper(II) using DMAP as chromogen by spectrophotometry.

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